

Global Prevalence of Stroke Among Patients with Atrial Fibrillation: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis 2025

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Article Info

Received: 27 August 2025

Revised: 31 August 2025

Accepted: 31 August 2025

Published: 8 September 2025

Keywords:

Atrial Fibrillation, Global, Meta-Analysis, Systematic Review, Stroke.

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ABSTRACT

Globally, it is estimated that there are 6.9 million cases of atrial fibrillation and 5.7 million disability-adjusted life years (DALY) due to ischemic stroke associated with atrial fibrillation. Studies show that atrial fibrillation is associated with a five-fold increase in the risk of stroke, and strokes caused by AF are often more fatal or result in severe disability. So this systematic review is aimed to estimate pooled global burden of stroke among patients with atrial fibrillation. Systematic search of published studies from PubMed, Scopus, web of Science, and manually on Google Scholar. This meta-analysis follows the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses guidelines. The quality of studies was assessed by the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale. Meta-analysis was carried out using a random-effects method using the STATA™ Version 14 software. The 12 studies included 95,736 participants. Most of the included studies were cross-sectional studies and conducted in Europe. All included studies had good methodological quality. The prevalence of stroke among AF patients ranges from 9.6% - 73.8%, with pooled prevalence of 21.4% (95% CI: 17.4- 25.5). The highest prevalence was 33.6 %; 95% CI: 22.6-44.7) seen in Europe and the lowest prevalence 11.4%; 95% CI: 2.9-19.9) was seen in Asia. The pooled global prevalence of stroke among patients with atrial fibrillation is significant. The sub-group analysis highlights notable regional variations. Clinicians should remain cautious in monitoring atrial fibrillation patients for stroke risk.

INTRODUCTION

Atrial fibrillation (AF) is increasingly recognized as a significant public health issue due to its prevalence and related complications. It is the most common type of cardiac arrhythmia, characterized by an irregular and often rapid heartbeat. AF results from high-frequency excitation of the atrium, leading to both dyssynchronous atrial contractions and irregular ventricular excitation (1-3).

The consequences of AF can be severe; it often increases the risk of stroke, heart failure, and other cardiovascular issues. The irregular rhythm can prevent the heart from pumping blood efficiently, which can cause blood to pool in the atria and form clots. If these clots travel to the brain, they can result in a stroke (4-6).

Globally, it is estimated that there are 6.9 million cases of AF and 5.7 million disability-adjusted life years (DALY) due to

ischemic stroke associated with AF (7). Furthermore, the incidence and prevalence of AF have risen over the past 20 years and are expected to continue increasing over the next 30 years, particularly in countries with a middle socio-demographic index. This poses one of the largest epidemics and public health challenges (8).

AF is highly prevalent, with an estimated lifetime risk of about 1 in 3 to 5 individuals after the age of 45. Additionally, the increased survival of the aging population with chronic diseases has contributed to the rising incidence and prevalence of AF, making it a common concomitant cardiovascular disease (10). In patients with AF, the fibrillation of the atrium leads to ineffective contractions, which results in blood stagnation. This stagnation favors thrombus formation, increasing the risk of embolization to the brain and subsequent stroke (11).

The incidence of atrial fibrillation and stroke is expected to rise worldwide in the coming decades due to the aging population and the growing prevalence of unhealthy cardiovascular habits (12). Studies show that AF is associated with a five-fold increase in the risk of stroke, and strokes caused by AF are often more fatal or result in severe disability (13, 14). Additionally, a greater burden of atrial fibrillation correlates with a higher risk of ischemic stroke, independent of known risk factors, particularly in adults with paroxysmal atrial fibrillation. So this systematic review is aimed to estimate pooled global burden of stroke among patients with atrial fibrillation.

Objective of the Study

To estimate the global prevalence of Stroke among patients with atrial fibrillation:

METHODS AND MATERIALS

Study Design and Search Strategy

In this systematic review and meta-analysis, the researchers utilized various databases, including PubMed, Scopus, PsycInfo, and Google Scholar. The Cochrane acronym POCC (Population, Outcome, Condition, and Context) was employed to guide the retrieval of studies across different databases, using appropriate medical subject heading (MeSH) terms and Boolean operator “AND” and “OR”. The search terms included “atrial fibrillation OR AFib AND neurologic event OR stroke OR emboli OR ischemic stroke AND adult OR young”. Additionally, manual searches were conducted. The researchers reported the findings in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses (PRISMA) 2020 guidelines (16).

Eligibility Criteria

Study period- this study included studies published up to August 2025.

Study type- this study included cross-sectional, case-control and cohort studies.

Language -this study included studies published in the English language.

Population-This study included studies that were conducted among patients with atrial fibrillation.

The study included studies both published and unpublished articles conducted in globally

Review articles (any type) and studies that did not report the desired outcome were excluded.

Data Extraction

After finalizing the searching, we conducted data extraction independently and exchanged the finding to verify the accuracy. Any discrepancies in extracted items were resolved through discussion. The extracted data was recorded in a Microsoft Excel 2013 spreadsheet and included the following information: author's name, publication year, study design, sample size, setting, and prevalence of stroke.

Data Outcome

The primary outcome of this review is to assess the prevalence of stroke among patients with atrial fibrillation.

Quality Assessment of Studies

The researchers utilized the modified Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS) for cross-sectional studies to assess the quality of studies. The scale consists of three components: selection, comparability and outcome assessment methods, with a total score of 10 points (17). Studies that scored five or higher on the NOS were included in the analysis (18). The quality assessment was independently conducted by all authors, and any discrepancy in the result was resolved through careful examination of the studies together.

Data Analysis and Synthesis Methods

After extracting the eligible studies, the data was exported to Stata software version 14 for analysis. A random-effect model was used due to the heterogeneity of studies, which varied across factors such as study setting, patient characteristics, demographics, and different risks for the outcome. Heterogeneity among the studies was assessed using Higgin's I² to quantify between-study heterogeneity. An I² test statistic of < 50 was declared as low heterogeneity, 50–75% was moderate, and > 75% was high heterogeneity (19). Sub-group analysis was conducted based on region of the study conducted. The funnel plot and Egger' test were utilized to check for publication bias; while sensitivity analyses were performed to assess the robustness of the synthesized results. Additionally Meta regression analysis was conducted.

RESULTS

Study Selection

Initially, a total of 7,977 studies were retrieved from the databases and manual searching. From this, 2,910 duplicate were found and removed. The remaining 5,067 articles were screened by their title and abstract and 4,575 irrelevant studies

were removed. 556 full-text articles were assessed for eligibility and 544 of them were excluded due not reporting the outcome of interest. Finally, a total of 12 studies was fulfilled the inclusion criteria and enrolled in the analysis.

The detailed retrieval process is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram of study selection on global prevalence of Stroke among patients with atrial fibrillation.

Study Characteristics

The 12 studies (20-31) included 95,736 participants. Most of the included studies were cross-sectional studies and the sample size ranged from 242(20) to 60594 (24). The prevalence of

stroke among AF patients ranges from 9.6% (22) - 73.8% (25). Most studies were conducted in Europe. All included studies had good methodological quality (Table 1).

Table 1. Characteristics of included study in this systematic review and meta-analysis.

Authors Name	Publication Year	Study area	Study design	Sample size	Prevalence with 95%CI
Gedamu Y,	2021	Gonder	Cross-sectional	242	19.2(14.2-24.1)
Gul N,	2025	Pakistan	Cross-sectional	345	13(9.4-16.5)
Son MK,	2017	Korean	Cross-sectional	14594	9.6(9.1-10.0)
Chao TF,	2014	Taiwan	Cohort	23723	12.7(12.2-13.1)

van den Ham HA,	2015	UK	Cross-sectional	60594	14.7(14.4-14.9)
Carlsson J,	2000	German	Cohort	369	73.8(69.3-78.2)
Hannon N,	2009	Ireland	Cohort	568	31.2(27.3-35.0)
Lin HJ,	1995	USA	Cross-sectional	656	17.5(14.5-20.4)
Béjot Y,	2009	France	Cross-sectional	3064	18.7(17.3-20.0)
Hayden DT,	2015	Ireland	Cross-sectional	568	31.2(27.3-35.0)
Miyasaka Y,	2005	USA	Cohort	4117	11(10.0-11.9)
Siu CW,	2014	China	Cohort	9727	21.8(20.9-22.6)

Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

CI: 17.4- 25.5), with heterogeneity index (I²) of 99.6% (p ≤ 0.001) (Figure 2).

Global Prevalence of Stroke Among Patients with Atrial Fibrillation

The pooled global prevalence of Stroke among patients with atrial fibrillation with a random-effects model was 21.4% (95%

Figure 2. Forest plot showing pooled global prevalence of Stroke among patients with atrial fibrillation.

Sub-Group Analysis

Sub-group analysis was conducted based on regions of the study conducted. The subgroup analysis result revealed that the

highest prevalence of Stroke among patients with atrial fibrillation was 33.6 %; 95% CI: 22.6-44.7), I² = 99.5%) seen in Europe and the lowest prevalence 11.4%; 95% CI: 2.9-19.9, I²= 99.8%) was seen in Asia (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Subgroup analysis of global prevalence of Stroke among patients with atrial fibrillation.

Publication Bias

The presence of publication bias was checked using the Egger’s test, and graphical by Funnel plot, the result egger’s test is not significant ($P = 0.984$). Also visual inspection of the funnel plot indicated asymmetrical distribution (Fig. 4), showing publication bias.

Sensitivity Analysis

Sensitivity analysis was done by removing studies step by step to evaluate the effect of a single study on the overall effect estimate. The result indicated removing a single study did not have a significant influence on pooled prevalence (Figure 5).

Figure 4. Funnel plot to test the publication bias in 12 studies with 95% Confidence limits.

Figure 5. Sensitivity analysis of pooled global prevalence of Stroke among patients with atrial fibrillation for each study being removed one at a time.

Meta-Regression

Due to high heterogeneity in subgroup analysis, we have conducted meta-regression to investigate the extent of statistical heterogeneity by using sample size and publication year as a covariate. The meta-regressions showed the sample size and publication year doesn't have effect on heterogeneity between studies (Table 2).

Table 2. Data regarding the meta-regression.

Heterogeneity source	Coefficients	Std. Err.	P-value
Sample size	.0001371	.0002615	0.611
Year of publication	-.0870852	.6404027	0.895

DISCUSSION

Many individuals with AF may not experience noticeable symptoms; it poses significant risks to cardiovascular health. One of the most serious complications associated with AF is the improper flow of blood within the heart, which can lead to the formation of blood clots. When the heart's atria do not contract effectively, blood can pool in these chambers. This pooling increases the chance of clot formation, especially in the left atrial appendage, if a blood clot dislodges and travels to the brain, it can cause a stroke (32)

The global prevalence of atrial fibrillation (AF) is approximately 60 million cases and contributes to >8 million disability-adjusted life year (33). On this study, the pooled global prevalence of Stroke among patients with atrial fibrillation with a random-effects model was 21.4% (95% CI: 17.4- 25.5). The findings from this pooled analysis is lower than

a global study conducted in some regions of the world (28%) (34). This discrepancy might be due to variation in sample size, demographic feature of the participants, life style , and comorbid condition of the study participants. Atrial fibrillation is linked to various risk factors such as age, hypertension, diabetes, and heart failure, which can exacerbate the likelihood of stroke (35, 36); these risk factors may be prevalent before a decade compared to recent time.

The recent findings emphasizes the importance of regular screening for stroke risk in patients with AF and highlight the need for effective anticoagulation strategies to mitigate this risk. Evidences showed that use of anticoagulant therapy reduces the risk of occurrence of stroke (37).

The subgroup analysis result revealed that the highest prevalence of Stroke among patients with atrial fibrillation was 33.6 %; 95% CI: 22.6-44.7), seen in Europe and the lowest prevalence 11.4%; 95% CI: 2.9-19.9 was seen in Asia. These variations could be influenced by a range of factors, including differences in healthcare access, differences in anticoagulation therapy practices, life style factors, demographic characteristics, underlying health condition, and management of atrial fibrillation across regions. In Europe, there may be more widespread recognition and diagnosis of atrial fibrillation, potentially leading to a more accurate representation of associated stroke risk.

This systematic review and meta-analysis it might have faced the following limitations. First, lack of meta-analysis conducted in other parts of the world make difficult for comparison. Secondly, due to presence of significant heterogeneity and presence of publication bias, the result should be interpreted cautiously.

CONCLUSION

The pooled global prevalence of stroke among patients with atrial fibrillation is significant. The sub-group analysis highlights notable regional variations. These findings emphasize the importance of regional healthcare strategies and interventions to address the varying risks of stroke in patients with atrial fibrillation. Furthermore, clinicians should remain cautious in monitoring atrial fibrillation patients for stroke risk, as early identification and management can lead to improved outcomes and reduced morbidity associated with strokes among these individuals.

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